

FUNDAMENTALS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF MANAGERIAL COMPETENCE OF SPECIALIZED PERSONNEL

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***Abstract.** Recently, special attention has been paid to improving the higher education system on the basis of ensuring a solid integration of science, education and production, based on the needs of the social sphere and economic sectors, training competitive personnel, effective organization of scientific and innovative activities, development of international cooperation, innovation in education management, further development of personnel management activities of specialized personnel, interaction and development of integration of education with industrial institutions.*

***Keywords:** education, management, management methodology, management activities, specialized personnel.*

Introduction. In the world's generally accepted concept of modern education, the management of the education system, assessment of the quality of education, improvement of processes, management tools and technologies are an urgent task. The training of competitive personnel is aimed at achieving social, economic and cultural progress through the consistent development of their managerial competence. The education system of countries such as the USA, Europe, South Korea, China, Singapore, and Japan leads the world in the application of new pedagogical strategies in the field of education. Therefore, it is important that specialists from leading higher educational institutions in the top 1000 be competitive, in demand on the international labor market, and possess the necessary competencies in the field of production in their specialty.

In recent years, significant work has been carried out in the country aimed at improving the mechanisms of organization and management of the educational process, the introduction of innovative education management based on democratic principles and a cluster approach to it, the introduction of advanced pedagogical technologies into the system of continuing education. The study of innovative processes in education, their functions, patterns of development, mechanisms and technologies for their implementation makes it possible to organize higher education institutions at the level of world standards based on the achievements of modern pedagogy and pedagogical science.

These requirements, in turn, oblige the design of the content of the development of managerial activities of managers based on the cluster approach in specialized personnel in the processes of integration of our country into the world economic system, the entry of national personnel into world labor markets, improvement of organizational and managerial mechanisms for the development of managerial activities, technologies for the development of effective managerial activities and managerial competence of managers.

Methods. Today, the effective operation of an educational institution largely depends on the quality of management in it. While the leadership potential and skills of the head of an educational institution determine the quality of this management, these characteristics themselves are based on the basic knowledge, skills, abilities and qualifications of senior staff.

The most subtle aspect of the management's activities is working with teachers and staff of the educational institution, as well as with students, organizing their joint activities, uniting the teaching staff on the way to one goal, gaining their respect and implementing healthy communication. This requires that the manager has knowledge, skills and competencies in the field of social psychology, art and communication skills, as well as communicative, constructive and organizational abilities. In developed countries, the following modern management activities are manifested in the management of education.

We have compared the management activities of higher educational institutions and organizations and the management functions throughout the organization are expressed as follows:

A goal-oriented function includes tasks in an organization's activities for a specific purpose.

Organizational function refers to the ability to effectively use the available capabilities of an organization.

It expresses the sequence of tasks required for the head to perform. Based on the above, we present the following particular functions from the main functions of the organization's management: planning, that is, the idea of what the target result will be, the stages and methods of achieving them.

The main principle in this is the coordination of the head and staff:

control refers to the activities of an organization, its resources, impulsiveness of management, as well as real activities in the main control and settlement process;

personal and pedagogical functions that control and ensure the functioning of the organization's employees within the framework of norms and rights accepted in society and at their own enterprise;

a social function in which there are differentiations in the activities and remuneration of various professions and the presence of workers in need of social protection.

The stimulating function consists in material and moral encouragement, which consists in ensuring a measure of compliance with performance discipline.

The goals and objectives of management determine managerial relations and regulate the competence of management, i.e. the principle of variability (variation) of the content and form of training - the approach of educational managers to the individual is relatively realized by orientation (attitude), assumes both independently and comprehensively the definition of goals and values.

Alternatively, the competence of specialists in personnel management of higher educational institutions in achieving the effectiveness of positive management between their staff and subjects of education embodies the following main functions:

motivational – formation of needs and interest in relation to innovative activities;

compensatory – the formation of the necessary qualifications of an education manager for the implementation of innovative activities;

corrective – provision of appropriate technologies;

predictive – training of specialized personnel to perceive innovative activities;

diagnostic – based on the importance of socio-psychological characteristics, the

management of specialized personnel provides for determining the level of preparation for the activity;

stimulating - support for positive training results;

information - promptly informing the manager about the effective experience of innovative activities;

advisory – scientific and methodological assistance of specialized personnel in solving specific tasks of innovative activity.

Based on theoretical analysis, online surveys and conclusions formed on the basis of empirical research, as well as on the basis of management requirements, the pedagogical system for organizing the process of developing managerial competence of specialized personnel of higher educational institutions based on the cluster approach mentioned above in the research process has been improved. Of course, we relied on the priorities of cluster policy in improving the managerial competence of specialized personnel based on the cluster approach.

This is manifested in the creation of scientific universities and the creation of interuniversity laboratories, the support of small innovative creative groups created on the basis of universities, the introduction of new forms of cooperation between universities specializing in the development of high technologies and the production of high-quality products, the possibility of highly qualified specialists in the field of science and higher professional education.

Results. Feedback. To successfully address the above issues, in our opinion, it is necessary: to provide all universities with modern equipment, laboratories and inventories; to form scientific and technical consulting resources for those interested in conducting research; to create specialized patent and marketing departments at the university; to put into practice, implement innovative research initiatives and create a fund to financial incentives for their activities, which gives a good effect.

The necessity of organizing and regularly passing academic staff of domestic and foreign scientific and industrial internships; participation in scientific and informational and scientific-practical seminars, conferences, symposiums, etc.; the need for financial incentives for the introduction of innovative methods of organizing the educational process and innovative ideas of a practical nature with the participation of students, senior researchers and applicants.

It is necessary to develop and implement innovative ideas and technologies for the training of specialized personnel, to produce innovations related to the integration of practical exercises into the educational process; to establish the involvement of student research teams in the activities of small enterprises.

It can be stated that most of the tasks currently listed have been implemented at our National Research University.

During the development of the managerial competence of specialized personnel, the questionnaire method was used to introduce a competence model and quantify the results of a communicative dialogue in management activities, increasing their readiness for management activities.

To assess the effectiveness of the model for the development of managerial competence of specialized personnel, the following criteria for assessing the readiness of specialized personnel for managerial activities have been developed:

1. Effectiveness: knowledge, communication skills; the ability to effectively apply the acquired knowledge and skills related to management activities in practice; managerial abilities.

2. Normativity: knowledge of the rules, instructions and legal documents governing the professional activity of a teacher-manager and the ability to apply them in activities.

3. Communication skills: communication with managers and their subordinates; the ability to individually approach the setting of tasks and control their implementation.

Table 3

Table of reflection of the dynamics of changes in experimental work

Indicators of the dynamics of changes	Criteria
Performance	Erudition, communication skills; the ability to effectively apply the acquired knowledge and management skills in practice; managerial abilities
Normativity	Knowledge of the rules, instructions, normative legal acts regulating the professional activity of the head teacher, the ability to apply them in activities
Communication skills	Engaging in a communicative dialogue with managers and their subordinates; the ability to individually approach the allocation of tasks and control over their implementation

Conclusions and recommendations.

In the development of communicative and managerial activities in the processes of managerial activity of specialists of educational institutions on the basis of ensuring interaction and integration of the factors indicated in the dissertation:

the personal and life position of specialists as active participants in social processes, their development as a full-fledged subject of innovative processes in an educational institution is determined;

the possibility of systematization of the goals of such functions as clarification of information, purposeful motivation, preliminary forecasting, planning, organizational and executive, control and diagnostic, regulatory and coordination, taking into account their orientation to personal and professional needs, interests.

Also, the creation of conditions for adaptation to the requirements of an innovative educational environment is scientifically and theoretically justified.

REFERENCES

1. Mustafoyeva D.A. Fundamentals of the development of managerial competence among teachers // Innovative development in the global science - 2022 г. Boston, USA Abstracts of VIII International Scientific and Practical Conference, 6-part, 91-97 pages.
2. Mustafoyeva D.A. Methods of developing critical thinking skills and cluster training in the educational process // pedagogical vocation – 2023 // Collection of articles of the International Professional Research Competition. – Russia: 2023. ISBN 978-5-00174-917-2. 22-28 pages.
1. 3.Zuhra Ismailova, Durдона Mustafoeva Technology for the development of media competence of students // Science and innovation international scientific journal volume 2 issue 2 February 2023 uif-2022: 8.2 // Issn: 2181-3337 // scientists.uz https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7612303

3. Kasimov J, Kamilov A., Mustafoyeva D.A. Building a 3D model of hydraulic structures using BIM technology J.A. // E3S Web of Conferences 402, 05021 (2023) <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202340205021>
4. Bezrukova V.S. (2004) Integration processes in pedagogical theory and practice. - Yekaterinburg, 152 p.
5. Belyaeva, A.P. (2002) Integrative theory and practice of multilevel continuing professional education / A.P.Belyaeva. – St. Petersburg: Institute of Vocational Education of the Russian Academy of Sciences, 240 p.